

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

New Evidence on the Seasonal Dynamics of Antarctic Intermediate Water and Its Role in Forming Modified Waters off Southern Patagonia

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This supplementary file provides monthly climatologies of wind and hydrographic variables in the study area around Southern Patagonia. Atmospheric data from the ERA5 reanalysis (1979–2018, near the surface) include wind direction and magnitude (S1) and Ekman transport, pumping, and layer depth (S2). Oceanic data from the Mercator model (1993–2024, 0.5 m depth) cover ocean currents (S3), conservative temperature (S4), absolute salinity (S5), potential density (S6), and water mass quantification (S7). These data complement the main article, which focuses on February and September, the months with the most significant variability. Details on data acquisition and calculations are provided in the main text.

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Figure S1. Monthly Climatology of Surface Winds

Figure S2. Monthly Climatology of Ekman Transport, Pumping, and Layer Thickness

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Figure S3. Monthly Climatology of Surface Currents

Figure S4. Monthly Climatology of Surface Conservative Temperature

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Figure S5. Monthly Climatology of Surface Absolute Salinity

Figure S6. Monthly Climatology of Surface Potential Density

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Figure S7. Monthly Climatology of Surface Water Mass Quantification